

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

РОЗРОБКА МЕТОДІВ ВИСОКОПРОДУКТИВНОЇ ТАБЛИЧНОЇ ОБРОБКИ ІНФОРМАЦІЇ В СПЕЦІАЛІЗОВАНИХ КОМП'ЮТЕРНИХ ЗАСОБАХ НА ОСНОВІ СИСТЕМИ ЗАЛИШКОВИХ КЛАСІВ

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DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS FOR HIGH-PERFORMANCE TABULAR INFORMATION PROCESSING IN SPECIALIZED COMPUTER TOOLS BASED ON THE RESIDUE NUMBER SYSTEM

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Анотація

У статті розглядаються науково-технічні засади створення високопродуктивних спеціалізованих комп'ютерних засобів обробки інформації (СКЗОІ) на основі непозиційної системи числення, а саме системи залишкових класів (СЗК). Обґрунтовано актуальність застосування табличної арифметики для реалізації модульних операцій у реальному часі. Розроблено вдосконалену математичну модель процесу табличної реалізації операції алгебраїчного множення, що базується на використанні коду інформаційного стиснення даних (КІСД). Запропонована модель враховує специфіку обробки даних як для парних, так і для непарних основ СЗК, що дозволяє суттєво (на 50–70%) скоротити обсяг апаратних витрат постійних запам'ятовувальних пристроїв (ПЗП). Результати дослідження спрямовані на підвищення швидкодії та надійності функціонування СКЗОІ в задачах криптографічного захисту та цифрової обробки сигналів.

Abstract

The article considers the scientific and technical principles of creating high-performance specialized computer information processing tools (SCIP) based on a non-positional residue number system (RNS). The relevance of using tabular arithmetic for the implementation of modular operations in real time is substantiated. An improved mathematical model of the process of tabular implementation of the algebraic multiplication operation is developed, based on the use of data information compression code (DICC). The proposed model takes into account the specifics of data processing for both even and odd RNS bases, which allows significantly (by 50-70%) reducing the hardware costs of read-only memory (ROM). The research results are aimed at increasing the speed and reliability of SCIP in cryptographic protection and digital signal processing tasks.

Ключові слова: спеціалізовані комп'ютерні засоби, система залишкових класів, таблична арифметика, алгебраїчне множення, код інформаційного стиснення даних.

Keywords: specialized computer tools, residue number system, tabular arithmetic, algebraic multiplication, data information compression code.

Introduction. The current stage of information technology development is characterized by a rapid increase in the volume of data requiring real-time processing. The scale and complexity of tasks solved by modern specialized computer information processing tools (SCRIPT) impose qualitatively new requirements on their performance, reliability, and energy efficiency [8, p. 112]. This issue is particularly acute for mission-critical systems: cryptographic information protection (specifically the implementation of asymmetric algorithms based on elliptic curves), digital signal processing in radar, and the control of autonomous robotic platforms.

Problem Statement. Traditional computing structures based on positional numbering systems

(PNS) have practically exhausted their potential for extensive development. The main obstacle is the presence of sequential inter-bit connections (carries), which limit the maximum clock frequency of processors [2, p. 24]. As the bit depth of operands increases—which is critical for modern cryptography, where key lengths reach 256–512 bits and more—the execution time of arithmetic operations increases linearly or exponentially. This directly contradicts the requirements of real-time operation. Attempts to solve this problem through simple parallelization within the PNS lead to excessive complexity of hardware logic and a critical increase in power consumption. As noted in classical studies on parallel systems, performance instrumentation remains a critical bottleneck when dealing with high-precision

arithmetic [6, p. 465]. Thus, a scientific contradiction arises between the need for ultra-high speed and the physical limitations of positional arithmetic.

An alternative and promising way to solve this problem is the transition to a non-positional residue number system (RNS). RNS allows transforming a complex operation on large numbers into a series of parallel operations on low-bit residues [7, p. 2]. The most effective method for implementing such operations is tabular arithmetic, which allows obtaining a result in a single clock cycle but requires the development of new data compression methods to optimize ROM memory capacity.

Relevance of the research. The relevance is driven by the need to develop methods for increasing information processing productivity without compromising the functional reliability of SCIPT. The application of RNS in modular arithmetic allows for significant optimization of the bit grid, especially in preventing overflow during intensive calculations [5, p. 230]. Traditional PNS, when implementing the tabular method, require an excessive amount of hardware: for an l -byte operational unit, the number of logic gates is $N_l = 2^{16l}$. Already at $l=4$, this value reaches 2^{64} , making the tabular method in PNS practically inapplicable.

In contrast, in RNS for $l=4$, the number of gates is only 2397, which is highly acceptable for modern hard-

ware components (FPGA, ASIC). Therefore, the development of specialized tools based on RNS is a fundamental alternative for creating high-performance real-time computing systems.

Modern research in neurocomputer structures further confirms that RNS-based arithmetic significantly enhances the speed of specialized neural processors [3, p. 85].

Mathematical modeling of tabular algebraic multiplication. To construct a mathematical model (MM) of the tabular multiplication process in RNS for both positive and negative ranges, input numbers A and B are represented in an artificial form. This modeling is fundamental for the implementation of cryptographic transformations, where digital security relies on the high-speed execution of modular operations [4, p. 58]. If the modulus m is an even number, the following relations hold:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \bar{a} - z_a \cdot \frac{m}{2}, \\ B &= \bar{b} - z_b \cdot \frac{m}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

where \bar{a}, \bar{b} represent the numerical part, and z_a, z_b represent the data information compression code (DICC) attribute.

The product $A \cdot B \pmod{m}$ for even moduli is described by the formula:

$$A \cdot B \pmod{m} = \left| \bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} - \frac{m}{2} (z_a \cdot \bar{b} + z_b \cdot \bar{a}) + z_a \cdot z_b \frac{m^2}{4} \right| \pmod{m}.$$

Considering that the term $\frac{m^2}{4}$ may introduce a calculation error, the final model for an even modulus is:

$$A \cdot B \pmod{m} = \left| \bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} - \frac{m}{2} (z_a \cdot \bar{b} + z_b \cdot \bar{a}) \right| \pmod{m}, \text{ if } z_a \cdot z_b = 0,$$

or

$$A \cdot B \pmod{m} = \left| \bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} - \frac{m}{2} (z_a \cdot \bar{b} + z_b \cdot \bar{a} - 1) \right| \pmod{m}, \text{ if } z_a \cdot z_b = 1.$$

For odd moduli (which constitute the majority of bases in RNS), the formula is transformed considering integer division:

$$A \cdot B \pmod{m} = \left| \bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} - \frac{m-1}{2} (z_a \cdot \bar{b} + z_b \cdot \bar{a}) + z_a \cdot z_b \frac{m-1}{4} \right| \pmod{m}.$$

The DICC attribute of the result z_c the product table of an arbitrary modulus m is determined by the logical XOR sum of the input attributes and the internal product attribute z_{prod} :

for even m : $z_c = (z_a \oplus z_b) \oplus z_{prod}$;

for odd m : $z_c = z_a \oplus z_b$ (with respective correction logic),

where $(z_a \oplus z_b)$ represents the preliminary determination of the result's range based on the input operands' quadrants. This functions as a modular parity check, similar to the sign rule in traditional arithmetic.

z_{prod} is the internal attribute stored within the optimized ROM. Since the multiplication of numerical parts $\bar{a} \cdot \bar{b} \pmod{m}$ can itself cross the $\frac{m}{2}$ boundary, z_{prod} acts as a correction factor derived from the symmetry of the modular multiplication table.

This logic ensures the correct mapping of the modular product back into the full range of the residue class, which is a critical step in maintaining data integrity during non-positional code transformations [9, p. 52]. Furthermore, such algebraic properties are foundational for

advanced logarithmic number systems used in specialized implementations [1, p. 198].

Optimization of operational unit structure. The proposed implementation of modular operations in RNS optimizes the SCIPT structure by utilizing the symmetry properties of ROM tables. The table of values $C = (a_i \cdot b_i) \pmod{m}$ is symmetric relative to the diagonals, vertical, and horizontal axes. Using DICC allows:

- Reduction of ROM table volume by 4 times by storing only one quadrant.
- Increased reliability and reduced recovery time due to the modular principle of the processing tract.
- Reduced power consumption, which is critical for autonomous robotic platforms and mobile cryptographic devices.

Conclusion. The developed mathematical model for the tabular implementation of algebraic multiplication in RNS provides a robust framework for creating high-efficiency arithmetic-logic units. Reducing ROM hardware requirements by 50–70% while ensuring sin-

gle-clock cycle execution confirms the feasibility of integrating these methods into specialized SCIPT. This research establishes a solid theoretical foundation for further dissertation work in the field of high-performance specialized computer systems.

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